

ODISSEI PORTAL User Guide

Authors: Laura Huis in 't Veld (DANS), Ricarda Braukmann (DANS), Deborah Thorpe (DANS), Angelica Maineri (ODISSEI)

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Introduction

ODISSEI

ODISSEI¹ (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations) is included in the Dutch National Roadmap Large-Scale Research Infrastructure, which was presented on 13 December 2016. ODISSEI has since then become an infrastructure with over 40 member organizations, including Dutch service providers (DANS, SURF), data collections (LISS panel), CBS, and academic faculties throughout the country. In May 2020, the Dutch Research Council (NWO) awarded ODISSEI with a large Roadmap grant² for further development.

ODISSEI Portal

The Data Facility work stream of the ODISSEI Roadmap project included the development of the ODISSEI Portal³. The ODISSEI Portal combines metadata from a wide variety of data providers into a single interface, allows advanced semantic queries to support findability, and facilitates data access⁴. Since December 2024⁵, the ODISSEI service is a stable service for Social Science researchers to find datasets available for reuse at Dutch repositories and other data providers.

Goal of this document

This document provides insight into the main functionalities of the ODISSEI Portal. It also contains information about the available metadata fields and their provenance for each Metadata Provider.

This document does not go into detail about the onboarding of new providers onto the Portal. Interested data providers can find general information for providers [here](#). The different routes providers can take are described there, and information about the metadata requirements for new providers are available [here](#).

¹ <https://odissei-data.nl/nl/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

² <https://odissei-data.nl/en/en-odissei/roadmap/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

³ <https://odissei-data.nl/facility/odissei-portal> (accessed 25/03/2025)

⁴ <https://portal.odissei.nl/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

⁵ <https://odissei-data.nl/2024/12/12/odissei-portal-from-prototype-to-production/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

Portal functionality

General information

The Portal can be freely accessed by anyone through:

<https://portal.odissei.nl/>

Per december 2024, the Portal contains metadata for datasets that are available from the following Dutch data providers:

- Statistics Netherlands (CBS)
- DANS Data Station for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)
- DataverseNL
- LISS Data Archive
- Historical Sample of The Netherlands (HSN)
- Consortium Individual Development (CID)

The portal does not contain the actual data files, rather users are able to search through all the **metadata** in the Portal. The Portal will also display information about licenses and terms and conditions for access if available. There is a connection with the Data Access Broker (DAB) - an interface through which users can access open access datasets and request access to restricted datasets (see section below).

The Portal is based on **Dataverse** software⁶, which is an open source repository software developed by Harvard University. The Dataverse software is designed for storing and searching datasets. The ODISSEI Portal only hosts metadata and we use the Dataverse functionalities to display and search through the metadata. We have altered the look and feel of the application a bit to reflect this: For instance, we removed the "File tab" and the button to download the data directly from the User Interface which is present in Dataverse instances used for archiving datasets.

Interface language

The user interface of the Portal is available in English (default language) and in Dutch. In order to use the Dutch user interface, the user can switch language by clicking the preferred language in the navigation bar at the top of the webpage.

Please note that only the user interface has a translation. The values of the metadata fields will remain in the original language, which is in English for most datasets but in Dutch for some (like CBS).

⁶ <https://dataverse.org/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

Searching for datasets

The ODISSEI Portal offers two search options, basic and advanced search.

Basic search

For basic search, the text box on the front page of the Portal can be used. This search bar accepts search terms, queries, or exact phrases (in quotation marks). The search will be performed in every available collection.

After entering a search term or query, results that match your term or query appear underneath the search bar, to the right of the [facets](#).

Each result shows which metadata fields match the search query or term you entered into the search bar, with the matching term or query bolded. If the search term or query was found in the title or name of the Dataverse collection or dataset, the search term or query will be bolded within it.⁷

Facets

The facets on the left side of the page can be used to narrow down the search results. Each facet will display the top five most common entries. If you would like to see more entries, click the 'More' link.

Distributor Name
Centraal Bureau voor Statistiek (1,298)
CentERdata (280)
DataverseNL (201)
Stichting Nationaal Monument Kamp Amersfoort (73)
Centerdata (70)
More...

Topic Classification Term
Bedrijven (319)
Arbeid en sociale zekerheid (284)
Gezondheid en welzijn (201)
Dossiers; Nederland regionaal (171)
Onderwijs (106)
More...

Fig 1. Screenshot of two facets from the ODISSEI Portal

⁷ From <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/6.1/user/find-use-data.html#id6> (accessed 25/03/2025)

The facets that will be shown depend on the selected collection. For example, the CBS collection will display a facet for 'Variable' whereas the LISS collection doesn't.

Advanced search

If you would like to perform a more specific search, you can click the 'Advanced Search' link next to the basic search text box. This will enable you to search within specific metadata fields, for example 'Universe' or 'Variable Label'. Please note that not every Metadata Provider uses the same set of fields, so this might affect your search results.

Fig 2. Screenshot of the Basic search textbox and the Advanced Search button.

Multilingual Search

We enrich metadata with terms from a Controlled Vocabulary (CV). In particular, datasets with keywords which match the terms present in the European Language Social Sciences Thesaurus (ELSST)⁸ receive a link to this CV as enrichment. The ELSST thesaurus is available in multiple languages. This allows users to find Dutch metadata records while searching with English terms from this vocabulary. More information about the available enrichments for each metadata provider is available in the relevant section below.

Machine access for metadata records in the ODISSEI Portal

Harvesting metadata

It is possible to harvest metadata records from the ODISSEI Portal using OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting). The base URL for the OAI-PMH endpoint is <https://portal.odissei.nl/oai>, and it is open to everyone. The following metadata formats are available:

- Datacite
- oai_dc (Dublin Core)
- oai_ddi (DDI Codebook 2.5)
- dataverse_json

⁸ <https://elsst.cessda.eu/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

Sets have been defined for each metadata provider. Use this link to see the set names: <https://portal.odissei.nl/oai?verb=ListSets>.

Downloading metadata with the API

The dataverse software offers different kinds of APIs to access the records in the Portal, for instance the Data Access API. This API however, is not very useful in the case of the ODISSEI Portal, because the records in the Portal only contain metadata.

What you can do to export the metadata of the current published version of a dataset in various formats, is use the following curl command:

```
curl  
"$SERVER_URL/api/datasets/export?exporter=$METADATA_FORMAT&persistentId=$PERSISTENT_IDENTIFIER"
```

In this command

\$SERVER_URL refers to the server in our case <https://portal.odissei.nl>
\$METADATA_FORMAT specifies the metadata format you want to receive
\$PERSISTENT_IDENTIFIER refers to the DOI of the dataset you want to retrieve.

For example:

<https://portal.odissei.nl/api/datasets/export?exporter=ddi&persistentId=doi:10.17026/dans-26q-ncb5>

The supported export formats are:

- ddi
- dcterms
- oai_dc
- schema.org
- OAI_ORE
- Datacite
- oai_datacite
- dataverse_json
- croissant

Indexing by search engines

The ODISSEI Portal makes use of a robot.txt file⁹ to indicate which services are allowed to index the webpages of the portal. The Portal is open for

⁹ <https://portal.odissei.nl/robots.txt> (accessed 25/03/2025)

Google Search and Bing. To help the search engines to crawl only the most important pages, a sitemap¹⁰ has been generated.

Data Access Broker

The ODISSEI Portal is connected to the Data Access Broker (DAB). The DAB is an interface through which users can access open access datasets and request access to restricted datasets. For every dataset, in the Terms tab, there is a link to the DAB. You can use this link to go to the DAB, where you can download Open Access Datasets directly. For restricted access datasets, the DAB currently links to the provider's page for more information. The DAB is currently still a prototype version and will be developed further. You can find more information on the DAB website¹¹.

Software and Code of the Portal

The Portal is based on Dataverse Software¹², in combination with an ingestion pipeline that has been specially developed for ODISSEI. The code and scripts that form the base of the Portal can be found in the ODISSEI Github repository¹³. The diagram below shows the different aspects in the workflow from metadata provider to Portal. Importantly we use a workflow orchestrator (using prefect software) which allows the different steps to be scheduled and logged.

¹⁰ <https://portal.odissei.nl/sitemap.xml> (accessed 17/04/2025)

¹¹ <https://dab.surf.nl/about/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

¹² <https://dataverse.org> (accessed 25/03/2025)

¹³ <https://github.com/odissei-data> (accessed 25/03/2025)

Fig 2. Schematic diagram of the technical steps taking from the metadata provider to the Portal. We follow an ETL Process where we Extract (yellow), Transform (green) and Load (Blue) the metadata.

For each dataset, there is a link in the Provenance metadata block that contains information about which workflows have been used to display the metadata. This way a user can see which actions were performed and which scripts were used to get from the original metadata to the information displayed in the Portal.

```

Save Copy Collapse All Expand All Filter JSON
{
  "_id": "67db76e6e5822b2e41716d17",
  "workflow_orchestrator": "v3.0.1",
  "created_on": "20-03-2025 02:00:36",
  "DANS-transformer-service": {
    "name": "DANS-transformer-service",
    "version": "0.5.9",
    "docker_image": "ekoindarto/dans-transformer-service:0.5.9",
    "endpoint": "https://transformer.labs.dansdemo.nl/transform-xml-to-json/true"
  },
  "dataverse-metadata-fetcher": {
    "name": "dataverse-metadata-fetcher",
    "version": "0.1.1",
    "docker_image": "fjodorvr/dataverse-metadata-fetcher:0.1.1",
    "endpoint": "https://dataverse-fetcher.labs.dansdemo.nl/dataverse-metadata-fetcher",
    "github_release": "https://github.com/odissei-data/dataverse-metadata-fetcher/releases/tag/v0.1.1"
  },
  "dataverse-importer": {
    "name": "dataverse-importer",
    "version": "0.1.1",
    "docker_image": "fjodorvr/dataverse-importer:0.1.1",
    "endpoint": "https://dataverse-importer.labs.dansdemo.nl/importer",
    "github_release": "https://github.com/odissei-data/dataverse-importer/releases/tag/v0.1.0-alpha"
  },
  "publication-date-updater": {
    "name": "publication-date-updater",
    "version": "0.1.1",
    "docker_image": "fjodorvr/publication-date-updater:0.1.1",
    "endpoint": "https://dataverse-date-updater.labs.dansdemo.nl/publication-date-updater",
    "github_release": "https://github.com/odissei-data/publication-date-updater/releases/tag/v0.1.0-alpha"
  },
  "metadata-refiner": {
    "name": "metadata-refiner",
    "version": "1.4.3",
    "docker_image": "fjodorvr/metadata-refiner:1.3.5",
    "endpoint": "https://metadata-refiner.labs.dansdemo.nl/metadata-refinement/datastation"
  }
}

```

Fig 3. Example of the provenance information stored in the metadata record of this example dataset in the ODISSEI portal. The example dataset is available at <https://portal.odissei.nl/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.17026/SS/EOLNNZ> and the displayed information can be reached through the link stored under "Provenance Metadata" the "Workflow Information".

Information about Metadata providers

The Portal aggregates metadata from different (Dutch) data providers.

This section provides information about the different sources, the available metadata per provider, mapping specifics and information about metadata enrichments that we performed. The paragraph below gives a quick overview, for more detailed information please refer to the relevant sections per data provider in the sections below.

Overview of all data providers available in the Portal

DANS Data Station SSH

- Endpoint for ingesting data:
https://ssh.datastations.nl/oai?verb=ListRecords&set=social_sciences&metadataPrefix=dataverse_json
- Mapping information available [on Github](#).
- Available enrichments: ELSST.

Statistics Netherlands (CBS)

- Endpoint for ingesting data: Not available. CBS provides DANS with metadata records on request.
- Mapping information available [on Github](#).
- Available enrichments: ELSST, CBS Taxonomie, CBS begrippen, Frequency of Use.

DataverseNL

- Endpoints for ingesting data: The general OAI-PMH endpoint is <https://dataverse.nl/oai/>. The following sets are harvested with metadataPrefix `dataverse_json`:
 - Avans_Social_Sciences
 - Fontys_social_sciences
 - Groningen_Social_Sciences
 - Hanze_Social_Sciences
 - HR_Social_Sciences
 - Leiden_Social_Sciences
 - Maastricht_Social_Sciences
 - PtHU_Social_Sciences
 - Tilburg_Social_Sciences
 - Trimbos_Social_Sciences
 - UMCU_Social_Sciences
 - UU_Social_Sciences

- VU_Social_Sciences
- TUDelft_Social_Sciences
- Twente_Social_Sciences
- ODISSEI_Social_Sciences
- Available enrichments: ELSST.

LISS Panel (Centerdata)

- Endpoint for ingesting data: https://www.oai-pmh.centerdata.nl/lissdata_json/. You will need a password to get access to this endpoint.
- Mapping information available [on Github](#).
- Available enrichments: ELSST, Linkage to CBS data.

Historical Sample of the Netherlands (HSN)

- Endpoint for ingesting data: https://datasets.iisg.amsterdam/oai?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=dataverse_json
- Mapping information available [on Github](#).
- Available enrichments: ELSST.

Consortium on Individual Development

- Endpoint for ingesting data: https://data.individualdevelopment.nl/oai?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oai_datacite
- Mapping information available [on Github](#).

DANS Data Station SSH

Source description

The DANS Data Station for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)¹⁴ allows users to deposit and search for data within the social sciences and humanities. The datasets deposited in this repository are curated and archived for long term preservation by DANS¹⁵.

Available metadata and mapping

The ODISSEI portal receives metadata from the SSH Data Station via OAI-PMH, only the datasets that have 'Social Sciences' as subject indication are harvested. The DANS Data Station SSH offers general metadata fields such as author name(s), title, description and funding information related material, as well as domain-specific metadata.

¹⁴ <https://ssh.datastations.nl/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

¹⁵ <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

For the SSH Data Station, the following metadata blocks are in use within the Portal:

- Citation metadata
- Social Sciences and Humanities metadata
- Geospatial Metadata
- DANS Specific metadata
- Enriched metadata
- Provenance metadata

The JSON file that is used for the mapping can be found in Github¹⁶.

For the exact mapping of each field, please take a look at the mapping file in [Zenodo](#).

Enrichment information

Enrichments are included from the ELSST. This is done by matching the original keywords and topic classification terms (in Dutch and English) with terms from ELSST. A table has been made with all the terms from the ELSST thesaurus¹⁷. This table includes both English and Dutch terms. If there is a 100% match with the value of the keyword or topic classification term metadata field, the relevant ELSST term is added. The added terms can be found underneath the 'Enriched Metadata' header, on the metadata-tab of the dataset page.

Statistics Netherlands (CBS)

Source description

The ODISSEI Portal hosts metadata of Statistics Netherlands (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, CBS) about their available Microdata.¹⁸

Microdata are linkable data about individuals, businesses and addresses that universities, scientific organisations, public policy and research institutes in the Netherlands and in a number of other EU countries can use – under strict conditions – to conduct their own statistical research. Safeguarding privacy and preventing the exposure of people or businesses are the key principles in granting access. The research is done in a secure microdata environment of CBS, the Remote Access Environment (RA environment).¹⁹

¹⁶ <https://github.com/odissei-data/mappings/blob/main/mappings/ssh-mapping.json> (accessed 25/03/2025)

¹⁷ <https://thesauri.cessda.eu/en/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

¹⁸ <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/onze-diensten/maatwerk-en-microdata/microdata-zelf-onderzoek-doen/catalogus-microdata> (accessed 25/03/2025)

¹⁹ <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/our-services/customised-services-microdata/microdata-conducting-your-own-research> (accessed 25/03/2025)

Available metadata and mapping

The ODISSEI Portal receives from CBS an XML file per datadesign. The XML files contain general metadata fields, but often also contain metadata about the variables that were used. The ingestion pipeline maps the metadata from these files to the metadata schema of the ODISSEI Portal.

For CBS, the following metadata blocks are in use:

- Citation metadata
- Social Sciences and Humanities metadata
- Variable Information
- CBS Specific metadata
- Enriched metadata
- Provenance metadata

The JSON file that is used for the mapping can be found in Github²⁰.

For the exact mapping of each field, please take a look at the mapping file in [Zenodo](#).

Additional steps are incorporated into the ingestion pipeline that processes the CBS files:

- DOI's are added for each record. CBS does currently not mint their own persistent identifiers for the metadata records. This is currently done during the ingest into the Portal.

The PIDs are minted as DOIs and this is done through DataCite which we provide with the identifier and a set of minimal metadata that DataCite stores in their registry.

The identifier we use is based on a standard prefix in combination with the Data Design ID from CBS. This ID is unique for every data design they have and this way the PID can easily be determined based on the data design ID.

Specifically, the DOI for a given DataDesign looks like this:

<https://doi.org/> [10.5793] [/DataDesignID]

During the ingest phase, a service is called that checks if a DOI is already available. If no DOI is found for the specific dataset, a DOI is registered by DataCite.

²⁰ <https://github.com/odissei-data/mappings/blob/main/mappings/cbs-mapping.json> accessed 25/03/2025)

- E-mail addresses are deleted from the metadata in order to prevent spam messages being sent.

Enrichment information

In the case of CBS, several enrichments are made:

1. Term ELSST

We enriched the CBS metadata by mapping the available Dutch keywords to terms in the ELSST. The added terms can be found underneath the 'Enriched Metadata' header, on the Metadata tab of the dataset page. The same enrichment procedure as described above for the SSH Data Station is used.

2. Terms CBS Taxonomie and CBS begrippen

Terms from Controlled Vocabularies hosted by CBS are also added, based on matching the already available keywords and topic classifications. If there is a 100% match between the value of the topic classification metadata field and a term from [the CBS taxonomy](#), this CBS Taxonomy term is listed as 'CBS Taxonomie' under the 'enriched metadata' header.

If there is a 100% match between the value of the keyword metadata field and a term from the CBS taxonomy, this term is listed as 'CBS begrippen' under the 'enriched metadata' header.

3. Frequency of Use

The CBS metadata is also enriched with information about the frequency of use. The frequency of use of CBS microdata has been calculated by the ODISSEI Coordination Team on the basis of the information on the Remote Access projects available [on the CBS website](#). Datasets were categorized as having a high, medium or low frequency of use depending on how often a dataset was requested. The list of datasets with its frequency of use can be found on Github [here](#).

The search results in the CBS section of the Portal are weighted on the basis of this frequency of use, so that records with a high frequency are shown at the top, making it easier for users to find relevant datasets. Also, hits on the commonly used 'Alternative title' are given a higher weight. The 'frequency of use' metadata field can also be found underneath the 'Enriched Metadata' header, on the Metadata tab of the dataset page.

DataverseNL

Source description

DataverseNL²¹ is a research data repository co-provided by DANS and participating institutions. DANS manages the technical infrastructure and the institutions using DataverseNL are responsible for granting rights to user accounts, managing and curating the deposited research data within DataverseNL.

The metadata hosted by the ODISSEI Portal encompasses only the datasets from DataverseNL that have 'Social Sciences' as subject indication. For each DataverseNL partner there is a separate section in the Portal with their metadata.

Available metadata and mapping

The ODISSEI Portal receives metadata from DataverseNL via OAI-PMH. The Portal harvests the OAI-PMH sets of the DataverseNL partners that contain datasets with the subject 'Social Sciences' indicated in the metadata.

DataverseNL records mainly contain general metadata fields, and do not often have domain-specific metadata fields.

For DataverseNL, the following metadata blocks are in use:

- Citation metadata
- Social Sciences and Humanities metadata
- Enriched metadata
- Provenance metadata

Because DataverseNL uses the same software - and metadata scheme - as the Portal, no special mapping is needed. In GitHub you can find the base-mapping²² that is used for the ingestion of the DataverseNL metadata records.

Enrichment information

In the case of DataverseNL, relevant terms from the ELSST are added. This is done by matching the original keywords (in Dutch and English) with terms from ELSST. The terms that have been added can be found underneath the 'Enriched Metadata' header, on the Metadata tab of the dataset page.

LISS

Source description

²¹ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/data-services/dataversenl/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

²² <https://github.com/odissei-data/mappings/blob/main/mappings/base-mapping.json> (accessed 25/03/2025)

The LISS panel²³ was founded in 2007 and is managed by the independent non-profit institute Centerdata²⁴, located on the campus of Tilburg University. Centerdata is an official partner of Tilburg University and utilises the LISS panel to collect research data through online surveys. These data are collected for scientific researchers and policy makers, primarily from the (experimental) social, economic, and behavioral sciences. However, researchers from other disciplines such as health, humanities, and digital sciences also make use of the LISS panel.²⁵

Available metadata and mapping

The Portal receives metadata from LISS via a JSON endpoint (see the overview at the beginning of this section for the link). The records from LISS contain general metadata fields and social sciences metadata fields. Most common are 'Collection Mode' and 'Characteristics of Data Collection Situation'. Additionally, metadata about the questionnaires that have been used is available for some datasets.

For LISS, the following metadata blocks are in use:

- Citation metadata
- Social Sciences and Humanities metadata
- Question Information
- Enriched metadata
- Provenance metadata

The JSON files are ingested in our pipeline, and a mapping to the metadata scheme of the Portal takes place. The JSON file that is used for the mapping can be found in Github.²⁶ For the exact mapping of each field, please take a look at the mapping file in [Zenodo](#).

It should be noted that the endpoint contains records for the LISS Core Studies, as well as separate records for each wave within a study. As this hierarchy cannot be easily reflected in Dataverse, the Portal only ingests the *higher level* studies. We chose to do this to prevent the search results becoming less useful by showing a higher level study and all of their waves as separate results.

Enrichment information

In the case of LISS, two kinds of enrichments take place.

1. Term ELSST

²³ <https://www.lissdata.nl> (accessed 25/03/2025)

²⁴ <https://www.centerdata.nl/> (accessed 25/03/2025)

²⁵ <https://www.lissdata.nl/about-us> (accessed 25/03/2025)

²⁶ <https://github.com/odissei-data/mappings/blob/main/mappings/liss-mapping.json>

We enriched the LISS metadata by mapping the available Topic Classifications to terms in the European Social Sciences Language Thesaurus (ELSST). The terms that have been added can be found underneath the 'Enriched Metadata' header, on the Metadata tab of the dataset page.

2. Linkage to CBS Microdata

The Portal adds information about linking a LISS dataset with CBS microdata. By design, individuals in the LISS panel can be linked to their records in the CBS microdata system. This will only be possible within the CBS RA environment, and only for the respondents that gave consent. Within the Portal, [a link to a webpage with more information about the linkage procedure](#) (in Dutch only) is displayed as a value for the field 'Linkage details'.

Historical Sample of the Netherlands (HSN)

Source description

The HSN offers a representative sample of about 85,500 people born in the Netherlands during 1812-1922. The HSN-database containing individual life-courses is a unique tool for research in Dutch history and demography. The HSN database will include information on an individual level from 85,500 persons on subjects like age at marriage, religious affiliation, the number of children born, occupation, birth place, literacy, social network and migration history.²⁷

Available metadata and mapping

The ODISSEI Portal receives metadata from HSN via OAI-PMH.

For HSN, the following metadata blocks are in use:

- Citation metadata
- Geospatial metadata
- Enriched metadata
- Provenance metadata

Because HSN uses the same software - and metadata scheme - as the Portal, no special mapping is needed. In Github you can find the [base-mapping](#) that is used for the ingest of the HSN metadata records.

Enrichment information

We enriched the HSN metadata by mapping the available keywords to terms in the European Social Sciences Language Thesaurus (ELSST). The terms

²⁷ <https://iisg.amsterdam/en/hsn> (Accessed 25/03/2025)

that have been added can be found underneath the 'Enriched Metadata' header, on the Metadata tab of the dataset page.

Consortium on Individual Development (CID)

Source description

The Portal includes metadata from the Individual Development Data Catalogue²⁸ which is a centralized metadata repository for six Dutch developmental cohort studies, collectively organized under the Consortium on Individual Development (CID). The data catalogue provides access to metadata that covers various measures related to child development.

Available metadata and mapping

The ODISSEI Portal receives metadata from CID via OAI-PMH.

For CID, the following metadata blocks are in use:

- Citation metadata
- Geospatial metadata (for Geographical Coverage - Country)
- Social Sciences and Humanities Metadata (for Collection Mode)
- Provenance metadata

The mapping of the CID fields to the fields in the ODISSEI Portal is done with XSLT. The file that is used for the mapping can be found in Github²⁹. For the exact mapping of each field, please take a look at the mapping file in [Zenodo](#).

Enrichment information

There are currently no enrichments performed on the CID metadata. This will be added in the spring 2025.

Contact Information

Please send an e-mail to portal@odissei.nl if you want to get in contact with the Portal team. In addition to questions and requests for support, we also appreciate your feedback!

²⁸ <https://data.individualdevelopment.nl/> (Accessed 25/03/2025)

²⁹ <https://github.com/odissei-data/mappings/blob/main/mappings/cid-oaipmh-to-dv-v1.xsl>